

Electrogenerated base : A green protocol for synthesis of arylidene malononitrile

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Abstract : A simple electrochemical synthesis of arylidene malononitrile from different aldehydes are studied and discussed here. A controlled potential electrolysis was carried out in undivided cell in the presence of acetonitrile as a solvent and lithium perchlorate as a supporting electrolyte. Electrogenerated base of malononitrile reacts with aldehyde substrate to give the corresponding product in excellent yield. This synthesis avoids addition of base as a catalyst and other toxic chemicals. Thus the method is environmentally benign and a contribution in the field of green chemistry.

Keywords : Electrogenerated base, platinum cathode, malononitrile, arylidene compounds, green chemistry.

Introduction

The arylidene compounds have numerous applications in the synthesis of carboxylic acid¹, heterocycles² and other fine chemicals³. Base catalyzed conventional synthesis of arylidene malononitrile was done by Knoevenagel condensation reaction in the presence of organic solvents⁴, Lewis acid⁵, surfactants⁶ and layered silicate⁷. Many investigations were aimed to find out a new and effective catalyst for the reaction but not a small effort was done to carryout reaction without these toxic catalysts.

With increasing public concern over environmental degradation, use of electrochemical technology can provide a valuable alternative to the conventional reagents for fine chemical synthesis⁸. Due to the electron transfer between an electrode and the substrate molecules the formation of highly reactive intermediates is achieved under mild conditions, avoiding acid and bases as reducing or oxidizing agent and related waste by-products.

In continuation of other electrochemical reaction, we made an effort to synthesize arylidene compounds without any base as catalyst. However, electrogenerated base of malononitrile reacts with aldehyde substrate to give product in excellent yield.

Results and discussion

The reaction with EGB was reported in 1968; anionic species generated in electroreduction acts as a base and prompted the formation of phosphonium ions from phosphonium salts⁹. In 1969 Iverson¹⁰ reported the electro-

reduction of azobenzene to corresponding anion radical which induces the Wittig reaction as EGB. In 1983 electroreduction of 2-pyrrolidone was carried out in DMF, using tetraalkylammonium salts as supporting electrolyte. This reaction evolved the corresponding anionic species possessing interesting reactivity as EGB¹¹. The anionic species generated in electroreduction usually act as a nucleophiles but sometimes they behave as a bases (electrogenerated bases, EGBs) having interesting reactivity.

The cathodic reduction of some organic compounds leads to the formation of intermediates that can behave as base (electrogenerated bases (EGBs)), nucleophiles or both. Usually EGBs are produced by reduction of compounds present to the reaction mixture. So we use malononitrile for synthesis of arylidene malononitrile. Evans¹² described the reduction of CH acid on Pt cathode in DMSO yielding conjugate base and dihydrogen.

This prompted us to study the reactivity of the CH-acid $\text{CH}_2(\text{CN})_2$ (1) versus aldehydic substrates (3) in CH_3CN containing LiClO_4 as a supporting electrolyte. The progress of the overall reaction was studied by a potentiostat and the rate of each chemical step was compared by voltammetric analysis.

Proposed mechanism :

R = CH₃, C₆H₅, 4-ClC₆H₄, 4-OHC₆H₄, 4-MeOC₆H₄, 4-NO₂C₆H₄, 4,4-*N,N*(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, 4-MeC₆H₄, C₄H₃O, C₅H₄N

Scheme 1

The cathodic reduction of malononitrile (1) leads to the formation of anion (2) which acts as electrogenerated base. This electrogenerated base undergoes condensation with aryl aldehyde (3) to form arylidene malononitrile (6).

Electrolysis :

Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out in three electrode cell assembly with 1 cm × 0.5 cm platinum electrodes¹³ as a working as well as a counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode¹⁴⁻²⁰ (SCE) as a reference electrode.

Experimental

Reaction mixture :

A solution of aryl aldehyde (10 mmol), malononitrile (having active methylene group) (10 mmol) and lithium perchlorate (0.1 M) was prepared in acetonitrile solvent (40 mL). The reaction mixture was electrolyzed under controlled potential. The current potential data was recorded by potential cum galvanostat and the reaction was completed within 4 to 5 h.

Solid product sticks at the wall of platinum cathode during electrolysis. A powerful magnetic stirrer was used to remove the deposition on the electrode. After electrolysis, the solution was filtered and product was rinsed with an ice cold ethanol/water solution (9 : 1, 5 mL). The

products were dried under reduced pressure and solid product was obtained in excellent purity and good yield. The products were analyzed by spectral technique.

Instrumentation :

The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX 400 (400 MHz) FT spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal reference. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm downfield from TMS as an internal reference.

Spectral analysis :

2-Isobutyridene-malononitrile (6a) : Oil (lit.²¹); IR (cm⁻¹) : 2223 (CN), 1591 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.04 (1H, s, -CH), 2.57 (1H, m, -CH), 1.12 (3H, d, CH₃), 1.14 (3H, d, CH₃); ¹³C NMR : δ 170.4, 117.2, 23.1, 21.1.

2-Benzylidene-malononitrile (6b) : Brown, solid; m.p. 84–85 °C (lit. 83 °C); IR (cm⁻¹) : 2223 (CN), 1591 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.98 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 7.94–7.92 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.66–7.62 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.57–7.51 (2H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR : δ 160.1, 134.6, 131.0, 130.7, 129.6, 113.8, 112.7, 82.6.

2-(4-Chloro-benzylidene)-malononitrile (6c) : Light brown, solid; m.p. 167–168 °C (lit. 165 °C); IR (cm⁻¹) : 2228 (CN), 1584 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 8.05 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 7.57–7.51 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR : δ 158.2, 141.2, 131.8, 130.1, 129.3, 113.4, 112.3, 83.4.

2-(4-Methoxy-benzylidene)-malononitrile (6d) : Brown, solid; m.p. 116–118 °C (lit. 119 °C); IR (cm⁻¹) : 2224 (CN), 1560 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.91 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.65 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 7.01 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 3.92 (3H, s, OCH₃); ¹³C NMR : δ 164.8, 158.8, 133.4, 124.0, 115.1, 114.4, 113.3, 78.7, 55.8.

2-(4-Nitro-benzylidene)-malononitrile (6e) : Yellow, solid; m.p. 158–160 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 2223 (CN), 1595 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.88–8.87 (1H, m, Ar-H), 8.57 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 8.55–8.42 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.98 (1H, t, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR : δ 159.3, 149.3, 136.5, 133.5, 131.8, 128.6, 125.7, 114.1, 113.1, 86.5.

2-(4-Hydroxy-benzylidene)-malononitrile (6f) : Brown, solid; m.p. 186–188 °C (lit. 183 °C); IR (cm⁻¹) : 2226

Table 1. Current-potential data recorded by potentiostat cum galvanostat during electrolysis

Sl. no.	Entry	Malononitrile	R	Time (h)	Potential (V)	Current (A)	Yield (%)
1.	6a	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	CH ₃	3	1.30	0.32	95
2.	6b	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	C ₆ H ₅	3	1.60	0.22	95
3.	6c	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	3	1.45	0.27	90
4.	6d	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4-HOC ₆ H ₄	4	1.82	0.17	88
5.	6e	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	5	1.65	0.21	90
6.	6f	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4	1.40	0.19	80
7.	6g	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4,4- <i>N,N'</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	3	1.32	0.30	85
8.	6h	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	4	2.10	0.12	72
9.	6i	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	C ₄ H ₃ O	5	1.40	0.15	70
10.	6j	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	C ₅ H ₄ N	4	1.90	0.23	85

Fig. 1. NMR spectra of the product **6c**.

(CN), 1587 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 10.42 (1H, broad signal, OH), 7.85 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.68 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 6.94 (2H, d, Ar-H), 5.98 (broad signal, 2NH); ¹³C NMR : δ 163.9, 159.0, 133.4 (2C), 122.4, 116.5 (2C), 114.4, 113.4, 75.8.

2-(4-Methyl-benzylidene)-malononitrile (6g) : Yellow, solid; m.p. 134–135 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 2220 (CN), 1590 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.82 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.73 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 7.34 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H), 2.46 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR : δ 159.8, 146.4,

130.9, 130.3, 128.4, 114.0, 112.8, 81.1, 22.0.

2-Furan-2-ylmethylene-malononitrile (6h) : Pale yellow, solid; m.p. 68–69 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 2223 (CN), 1597 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.81 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz, furyl), 7.52 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 7.37 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz, furyl), 6.73–6.71 (1H, m, furyl); ¹³C NMR : δ 149.6, 147.9, 143.0, 123.6, 114.4, 113.8, 112.6.

2-(4-Dimethylamino-benzylidene)-malononitrile (6i) : Yellow, solid; m.p. 180–182 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 2222 (CN), 1590 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.81 (2H,

Table 2. Comparison between chemical and electrochemical synthesis of arylidene malononitrile

Sl. no.	Malanitrile	R	Energy input		Temperature		Time (h)		Yield (%)		Ref.
			Reagent/Catalyst								
			CS ^a	ES ^b	CS	ES	CS	ES	CS	ES	
1.	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	CH ₃	MgBr ₂ .OEt ₂	Current 0.32 A	RT	RT	2	3	98	95	22
2.	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	C ₆ H ₅	Cl(CH ₃) ₃ Si	Current Heating 0.22 A	100 °C	RT	10	3	95	92	23
3.	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4-ClC ₆ H ₅	SO ₄ ²⁻ /ZrO ₂	Current Heating 0.27 A	100 °C	RT	2	3	38	85	26
4.	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4-HOC ₆ H ₅	Ethanol	Current 0.17 A	RT	RT	24	4	48.5	88	25
5.	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4-MeOC ₆ H ₅	SO ₄ ²⁻ /ZrO ₂	Current Heating 0.21 A	100 °C	RT	2.5	5	80	85	24
7.	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	4,4- <i>N,N'</i> - (CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₅	CTMAB	Current 0.30 A	RT	RT	1.5	3	73	79	25
9.	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	C ₅ H ₄ N	SO ₄ ²⁻ /ZrO ₂	Current Heating 0.23 A	100 °C	RT	0.58	4	92	85	24
10.	CH ₂ (CN) ₂	C ₄ H ₃ O	[2-Aemim][PF ₆] three step reaction	Current 0.15 A	RT	RT	2	5	90	70	27

^aConventional/chemical synthesis.^bElectroorganic/electrochemical synthesis.

d, *J* 9.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.46 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 6.69 (2H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz, Ar-H), 3.14 (6H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR : δ 158.0, 154.2, 133.8, 119.2, 116.0, 115.0, 111.5, 71.6, 40.1.

2-Pyridin-2-ylmethylene-malononitrile (6j) : Black, solid; m.p. 84–85 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 2223 (CN), 1585 (C=C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.89 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, pyridyl), 8.83 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz, pyridyl), 8.49–8.47 (1H, m, pyridyl), 7.55–7.52 (1H, m, pyridyl); ¹³C NMR : δ 158.5, 154.6, 152.3, 135.6, 126.9, 124.2, 112.9, 111.9, 85.5.

Electrochemical synthesis of arylidene malononitrile has advantages over conventional synthesis (Table 2). It can be performed at room temperature and use of toxic reagents and catalysts can be avoided. Catalytic amount of electricity as a non-conventional energy source for activation of reactants in suitable solvents has now gained popularity over the usual homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions. It provides processes with special attributes such as enhanced reaction rate, higher yield of pure products, better selectivity and several eco-friendly advantages.

Conclusion :

One pot electrochemical synthesis of arylidene

malononitrile was carried out in organic medium at room temperature using simple supporting electrolyte. Use of electrochemically generated base is special feature of this reaction because the reaction proceeds with sufficient rate in absence of external catalyst. Thus the method is environmentally benign and a contribution in the field of green chemistry.

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